

Assessing the Awareness and Adoption of NFT Technology Among Sri Lankan Digital Artists.

Sandali Jayakody¹, Lasith Gunawardena², Prabhasara Athurupane³

Department of Information Technology, Faculty of Management Studies and Commerce
University of Sri Jayewardenepura

191158@mgt.sjp.ac.lk, [2lasith@sjp.ac.lk](mailto:lasith@sjp.ac.lk), [3prabhasara@sjp.ac.lk](mailto:prabhasara@sjp.ac.lk)

Introduction

Background of the Study

Non-fungible tokens (NFTs) are digital tokens that represent unique ownership of a specific digital asset, such as video games, collectibles, or digital artwork. NFTs are typically exchanged in online marketplaces using cryptocurrencies and are recorded on a public blockchain, which ensures their uniqueness and evidence of ownership (Sharma et al., 2022). The NFT market experienced a significant surge in 2021, with sales reaching \$340 million in just two months (Kugler, 2021). However, the market is now facing a notable crash in sales due to the ongoing crypto crash and other factors. Despite this, some experts believe that the demand for NFTs is driven by the actual demand and value for digital uniqueness and collectibles, rather than just crypto values (Trautman, 2021). This study focuses on the nature of the NFT ecosystem in the Sri Lankan context by investigating the behavioral aspect of adopting NFT from the perspective of digital creative artists.

Problem Statement

Most of the existing research focuses on technical aspects of NFT, neglecting the behavioral aspects of adoption, especially from the perspective of digital artists. (Chalmers et al., 2022) Similar research

suggests that the NFT arts and its impact on creative digital artists and the creative industry should be explored further and extended including participants from different countries and regions (Catindig et al., 2023).

Research objectives

1. To examine the engagement, awareness, and knowledge of Sri Lankan digital artists about the NFT technology.
2. To understand how Sri Lankan artists, perceive and react to the global trends revolving around NFTs.
3. To understand the impact of NFT technology on the Sri Lankan digital creative designing industry in short term and long term.
4. To understand the challenges and barriers faced by Sri Lankan digital artists when learning and engaging with NFT technology.

Methodology

This study was qualitative and exploratory, and aimed to better understand the behavioral aspects of NFT adoption from the perspective of digital artists in Sri Lanka. The study sought to gain an enhanced understanding of the subject through direct interaction with the artists to explore the relatively novel phenomenon, which was not easily quantifiable or comprehensible (Aspers & Corte, 2019). The study adopted an inductive approach, drawing concepts, hypotheses, and themes from gathered data rather than deductive testing. The qualitative approach was suitable for phenomena where related underlying variables were unidentifiable and immeasurable, and the context needed to be explored to obtain a holistic understanding of the issue (Creswell, 2013).

The study considered all professional artists in Sri Lanka who utilize digital technologies in the creative and presentation processes of their artworks as the target population. To conduct this qualitative study, a sample of eight creative digital artists was selected, with the adequacy of the sample size determined through peer review and judgment. Several methods were employed to recruit artists for interviews, including direct messaging via LinkedIn, contacting administrators of NFT communities on Facebook for artist lists, and utilizing snowball sampling. Data collection involved conducting semi-structured interviews, with the interview questionnaire developed based on existing literature and tailored to the specific research questions. For data analysis, the research employed an inductive thematic analysis approach. Initially, interview transcripts were thoroughly reviewed to gain familiarity with the data before coding. The QDA Miner Qualitative data analysis tool was used to manage, code, and analyze the collected data. Codes were subsequently grouped into sub-themes, leading to the formulation of the main themes for the research findings.

Results and Discussion

Results

To examine the engagement, awareness, and knowledge of Sri Lankan digital artists about the NFT technology.

Different ways of occupying with NFTs

Responded artists were engaging with NFTs in different ways such as converting their own artworks and creating NFTs, taking orders for creating

NFT projects through freelancing platforms, taking part in these projects on sub-order basis and being occupied in companies that are developing NFT related products.

Financial gain is the leading motivation for engaging with NFTs among other motivators.

All the respondents stated that financial gain is the main motivation for them to engage with NFTs, as it offers new earning opportunities. However, artists are also driven by exploring new technologies, creating a positive impact, expressing their art, and gaining exposure.

Artists do not possess in-depth knowledge of NFT related technologies.

Artists had differing opinions on the level of technology knowledge required to work with NFTs. Some believed that an artist could work with NFTs without in-depth knowledge of the technology, while others thought that artists needed to understand at least the basics of smart contracts and blockchains to survive in the long run.

To understand how Sri Lankan artists, perceive and react to the global trends revolving around NFTs.

Opportunistic reaction to capitalize the trend

According to the study, Sri Lankan artists have been able to earn substantial profits by adopting NFTs and finding new ways to work with them. They have created new business models by forming self-structured entities or hubs that bring together artists and other skilled people to deliver NFT projects. These groups have made NFT collections on an order basis for specific clients and have carefully arranged the phases of NFT projects and delegated them to people with different specialties. Some participants

mentioned the reaction to long-term utilities of NFTs in Sri Lanka, with emerging innovative companies focused on sustainable business cases for NFTs in the Sri Lankan context.

Positive perception about the Future of NFTs

The participants in the study have a positive perception about the future of NFTs despite the current downfall of the NFT market. They agreed that digital art is only one utility case of NFTs and that there are many other potential uses for NFTs. Some of the participants supported their positive perception with reasons and didn't see the ongoing situation as a catastrophe but rather as a crash of a sudden bubble created around NFTs. They perceive this crash as a positive phenomenon that helps filter away the scammers from the marketplace and the ones that remain are serious investors, innovators, and artists looking to build great solutions with NFTs.

Supportive nature of NFT communities

The study found that all participants highlighted the supportive nature of NFT communities, both locally and internationally. The participants explained that the online presence of these communities on platforms like Facebook, Telegram, and Discord helps connect NFT artists with clients, facilitate networking, provide a space for artists to learn more about NFTs and new advancements in related technologies, enhance the exposure of their globally, and help artists stay updated on the new advancements and trends of NFTs.

To understand the impact of NFT technology on the Sri Lankan digital creative designing industry in short term and long term.

According to participant responses, NFT technology has had a significant impact on the digital arts industry in Sri Lanka by providing opportunities for artists to gain more work and connections with foreigners. However, the long-term impact of NFT technology on Sri Lankan artists is uncertain. Some participants pointed out that Sri Lankan artists must do something innovative and sustainable in the NFT space to gain a good reputation in the global market and avoid being recognized as only average artists in the future.

To understand the challenges and barriers faced by Sri Lankan digital artists when learning and engaging with NFT technology.

The participants pointed out some challenges and barriers they have faced when learning and engaging with NFT marketplaces which can be summarized as, the lack of marketing and project management skills, the difficulty of establishing mutual obligation between the client and the artist, and the impact of ongoing economic crisis in Sri Lanka.

Discussion

A variety of motivators to create and engage with NFT

The study by (Sharma et al., 2022) found that artists create NFTs for various reasons, including self-expression, emotional pleasure, sense of accomplishment, and being part of an innovative trend. Furthermore, a similar research study conducted in the Philippines revealed that digital artists exhibit a strong inclination toward embracing NFTs due to the financial benefits associated with NFT involvement, the opportunities it offers for career advancement, and its capacity to enhance the creativity and artistic freedom (Catindig et al., 2023). The study also found that Sri

Lankan artists have similar motivations, but they were not emphasized by interviewees, who primarily emphasized financial gain as the most important factor.

Collaboration and mutual support in NFT communities and groups

According to (Sharma et al., 2022), NFT communities and groups promote a collaborative learning culture. (Vasan et al., 2022) found that social networking among artists increases the income for artists as clusters. Furthermore, a similar research study conducted in Malaysia discovers the inadequate collaboration and participation between artists in Malaysia in the context of NFTs and suggests that participation and support among both new and traditional creators would help create a healthy ecosystem for NFT (Amirza et al., 2023). However, in Sri Lanka, communities are more focused on building connections and transactions, making knowledge sharing the second priority.

Difficulty in coping up with advanced technology

In the study by (Sharma et al., 2022), most artists had to struggle to learn new concepts and technologies of NFT. However, in Sri Lanka, most artists work with a team to create NFTs for client orders, so the technical part is handled by knowledgeable people in the team. Even artists who make NFTs out of their own unique artworks, tend to get the technical part done by someone else.

Conclusion

This study explores the impact of non-fungible tokens (NFTs) on the digital arts industry in Sri Lanka. Through interviews with eight artists across the country, it provided valuable insights into the artists' perspectives on NFTs.

The research examined their engagement, awareness, knowledge, perceptions of the future, and reactions to global NFT trends. Additionally, it explored the influence of NFTs on the Sri Lankan digital arts industry and identified the challenges and barriers faced by artists when adopting this technology. This study contributes to a deeper understanding of NFT adoption among Sri Lankan artists, offering crucial insights for both artists and stakeholders in the creative digital arts sector.

References

1. Amirza, M. A., Razak, M. R. A., Kamaruzaman, M. F., & Anwar, R. (2023). Non-Fungible Token (NFT) in Malaysian Creative Arts: The Status Quo of Tokenisation. *2023 IEEE 13th Symposium on Computer Applications & Industrial Electronics (ISCAIE)*, 299–303. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCAIE57739.2023.10165499>
2. Aspers, P., & Corte, U. (2019). What is Qualitative in Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Sociology*, 42(2), 139–160. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11133-019-9413-7>
3. Catindig, M. W. S., Garcia, C. M., Rustia, R. A. A., & Rojo, J. J. A. (2023). *The Potentials of NFT Art and Its Rising Opportunities for Filipino-Creative Industry Artists*. 420–425. <https://doi.org/10.1109/icbir57571.2023.10147659>
4. Chalmers, D., Fisch, C., Matthews, R., Quinn, W., & Recker, J. (2022). Beyond the bubble: Will NFTs and digital proof of ownership empower creative industry entrepreneurs? *Journal of Business Venturing Insights*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbvi.2022.e00309>

5. Creswell, J. W. (2013). *Qualitative Inquiry And Research Design - Choosing Among Five Approaches* (3rd ed.). SAGE Publications, Inc.
6. Kugler, L. (2021). Non-fungible tokens and the future of art. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(9), 19–20. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3474355>
7. Sharma, T., Zhou, Z., Huang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2022). “It’s A Blessing and A Curse”: Unpacking Creators’ Practices with Non-Fungible Tokens (NFTs) and Their Communities. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2201.13233>
8. Trautman, L. J. (2021). Virtual Art and Non-fungible Tokens. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3814087>
9. Vasan, K., Janosov, M., & Barabási, A. L. (2022). Quantifying NFT-driven networks in crypto art. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-05146-6>